

School Heads' Motivational Language and Teachers' Organizational Support in Bangoy District

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Abstract. This study aimed to determine which domains of school head's motivational language could significantly influence the teacher's perceived organizational support. The study utilized a descriptive correlational design. A total of 74 teachers in Bangoy District, Davao City Division were identified through tabachnick and fidell formula. The researcher utilized a two adapted questionnaire in the gathering of data. Mean, Pearson r, and multiple linear regression were used as statistical tools of the study. Results revealed on the level of school head's motivational language was moderate which means that it was sometimes evident. On the other hand, on the level of teacher's perceived organizational support was moderate, which also means that it was sometimes evident. Moreover, the results revealed that there is a significant relationship between school head's motivational language and teacher's perceived organizational support. Thus, the null hypothesis was rejected since the value denotes of having a significant relationship. Lastly, based on the regression analysis, the results revealed that the school head's motivational language significantly influences teacher's perceived organizational support. Thus, it was recommended that school heads should consistently apply motivational language strategies by giving clear directions, showing empathy, and reinforcing meaningful goals to inspire and support teachers more effectively.

KEY WORDS

1. Motivational language 2. Organizational Support 3. School heads
Teachers 4. descriptive-correlational

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1. Introduction

The behavior, attributes, and interactions of leaders with their employees play a vital role in achieving organizational goals. Management-staff dynamics can be analyzed from various comprehensive perspectives, yet a crucial aspect in sustaining effective communication is the use of motivational language by leaders. The way a leader communicates has a significant impact on employee engagement. Therefore, clear and effective communication between leaders and their teams—especially in the educational sec-

tor between school leaders and teachers—is of paramount importance.

Globally, the relationship between motivational language and perceived organizational support has been widely studied. In Turkey, Alev (2024) examined how school administrators' use of motivational language impacts teachers' perceptions of organizational support and their engagement at work. The study found strong positive relationships among these variables, with perceived organizational support par-

tially mediating the connection between motivational language and job involvement. The findings suggest that the way administrators communicate is a key factor in influencing teachers' commitment, both directly and indirectly.

In the Philippines, Fernan et al. (2022) investigated how motivational language from leaders affects faculty job satisfaction, focusing on communication that provides direction, shows empathy, and creates meaning. Their findings showed that leaders enhance job satisfaction by keeping faculty informed, supporting professional development, and recognizing individual contributions. The study recommended that college deans improve communication through regular meetings and orientations while encouraging feedback and recognizing excellent performance.

Despite the existing body of literature emphasizing the role of leadership communication in employee motivation and organizational outcomes, there remains a significant gap concerning the direct relationship between school leaders' motivational language and teachers' perceived organizational support—particularly in Davao City. While research often explores the broad effects of motivational language on employee motivation and satisfaction, it tends to overlook how such communication shapes teachers' views of the support they receive. Addressing this gap is crucial for developing leadership practices that resonate with the specific needs of educators in Davao City, ultimately leading to more effective leadership in the local educational and cultural setting.

The objective of this study was to examine the influence of school heads' motivational language on teachers' perceived organizational support in Bangoy District, Davao City Division. Specifically, it aimed to determine the level of motivational language used by school heads in terms of direction-giving/uncertainty reducing language (perlocutionary), empathetic language (illocutionary), and meaning-making language

(locutionary); assess the level of teachers' organizational support in terms of personalized, collectivistic, monistic, and teleological dimensions; investigate the significant relationship between school heads' motivational language and teachers' perceived organizational support; and identify which specific domain of motivational language significantly influences the perceived organizational support of teachers.

The hypotheses of the study were tested at the 0.05 level of significance. The first null hypothesis (Ho1) stated that there is no significant relationship between school heads' motivational language and teachers' organizational support. The second null hypothesis (Ho2) proposed that none of the domains of school heads' motivational language significantly influences teachers' organizational support.

The study's findings underscored the crucial role of school heads' motivational language in shaping teachers' perceptions of organizational support, offering valuable insights for educators, administrators, and policymakers. Teachers benefited from increased clarity, empathy, and shared meaning in communication, leading to a stronger sense of support and belonging in the workplace. School heads were encouraged to enhance their use of motivational language, especially in providing direction and emotional reassurance, to improve organizational climate. The Department of Education could utilize these findings to refine leadership training programs and communication standards. Furthermore, the study offered a foundation for future researchers to examine how motivational language influences other aspects of school performance, including teacher retention and student outcomes.

Figure 1 illustrated the conceptual framework of the study, which identified school heads' motivational language as the independent variable, comprising direction-giving/uncertainty reducing language (perlocutionary), empathetic language (illocutionary), and meaning-making language (locutionary). The dependent variable

Fig. 1. Conceptual Framework

was teachers' perceived organizational support, measured in terms of personalized, collectivistic, monistic, and teleological support dimensions.

2. Methodology

The following section outlines the procedures used by the researcher to perform this research study. It includes the population and sampling, instrumentation, data source, and data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study used a descriptive-correlational design to examine the relationship between school leaders' motivating language and teachers' perceived organizational support. The descriptive aspect identified trends in motivational language and organizational support, while the correlational part analyzed the statistical association between these variables without experimental intervention, aiming to determine how leaders' communication affects teachers' perceptions of support

2.2. Ethical Considerations—The researcher strictly adhered to the ethical guidelines outlined by RMC's Research Ethics, ensuring the study upheld principles such as informed consent, participant safety, privacy, and transparency. All participants voluntarily joined after being fully informed, and extra care was taken due to their professional vulnerability within a hierarchical setting. Risks were minimized through anonymization and voluntary participation, while benefits included insights for im-

proving leadership communication and school climate. The researcher was academically qualified and received mentorship to ensure proper study execution. Adequate facilities and expert guidance supported the research, and all data were handled confidentially in line with the Data Privacy Act. Measures were also taken to avoid conflicts of interest, ensure fair treatment, and present findings objectively and transparently.

2.3. Research Participants—This study involved 74 elementary school teachers from the Bangoy District, Davao City Division, selected using Tabachnick and Fidell's (2007) formula for regression analysis and chosen through stratified random sampling to ensure subgroup representation. Participants met specific inclusion criteria: permanent employment in the district and at least three years of teaching experience, ensuring relevant expertise. The sample size was based on one independent variable—school heads' motivational language, which included direction-giving, empathetic,

and meaning-making language.

2.4. Research Instrument —This study used a modified survey to assess school leaders' motivating language and teachers' perceived organizational support. The motivational language questionnaire, adapted from Mayfield et al. (1998), included 15 items across three dimensions: direction-giving, empathic, and meaning-making language. The organizational support instrument was based on the PCMT Model by Matusik et al. (2023), with both tools using a 5-point Likert scale. Content validation was conducted by experts, and a pilot test confirmed reliability, with scores of .85 for the motivating language scale and .80 for the organizational support scale, indicating strong reliability.

2.5. Data Gathering Procedure —To ensure comprehensive and reliable data collection, the study followed several key steps. Formal permission was obtained from institutional authorities, and ethical protocols regarding con-

sent and confidentiality were strictly observed.

The survey instruments underwent content validation by experts and were pilot-tested with 30 non-participating educators, resulting in minor revisions for clarity and reliability. Questionnaires were distributed both online via Google Forms and in-person through drop boxes, allowing flexible participation. Responses were collected using the same methods and securely stored to maintain data integrity. Data were analyzed using Mean, Standard Deviation, Pearson r, and Linear Regression to explore relationships and predictive factors.

2.6. Data Analysis —The study used the following statistical tools: Weighted Mean to assess the levels of school heads' motivational language and teachers' organizational support; Pearson r to examine the relationship between these two variables; and Linear Regression Analysis to determine the influence of school heads' motivational language on teachers' organizational support.

3. Results

This section highlighted the results and discussion of the study. The presentation starts from the descriptive analysis of school heads' motivating language and teachers' perceived organizational support, followed by the discussion on the correlation between the two variables. The presentation ends with the domains of school heads' motivating language that significantly influences teachers' perceived organizational support.

3.1. Level of School Heads' Motivating Language —Table 1 shows the level of school heads' motivating language which is measured by three indicators namely: Direction-Giving/Uncertainty Reducing Language (Perlocutionary), Empathetic Language (Illocutionary), and Meaning-making Language (Locutionary). The mean ratings of these indicators are as follows: Direction-Giving/Uncertainty Reducing Language (Perlocutionary) (3.39) was described as moderate, equivalent to sometimes evident. Empathetic Language (Illocutionary)

(3.34) was described as moderate, equivalent to sometimes evident. Lastly, Meaning-making Language (Locutionary) (3.17) was described as moderate, equivalent to sometimes evident. The overall garnered mean was (3.30) which was described as moderate. This means that the level of school heads' motivating language namely: Direction-Giving/Uncertainty Reducing Language (Perlocutionary), Empathetic Language (Illocutionary), and Meaning-making Language (Locutionary) was moderate and was sometimes observed among school heads of Davao City Division.

Table 1. Level of School Heads’ Motivating Language

No.	Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Direction-Giving/Uncertainty Reducing Language (Perlocutionary)	3.51	High
2	Empathetic Language (Illocutionary)	3.21	Moderate
3	Meaning-making Language (Locutionary)	3.34	Moderate
Overall Mean		3.31	Moderate

3.2. *Level of Teachers’ Perceived Organizational Support* —Table 2 shows the level of teachers’ perceived organizational support which is measured by four indicators namely: personalized organizational support, collectivistic organizational support, monistic organizational support, and teleological organizational support. The mean ratings of these indicators are as follows: personalized organizational support (3.29) was described as moderate, equivalent to sometimes evident. Collectivistic organizational support (3.49) was described as high, equivalent to oftentimes evident. Monistic

organizational support (3.33) which was also described as sometimes evident. Lastly, teleological organizational support (3.39) was described as moderate, equivalent to sometimes evident. The overall garnered mean was (3.36) which was described as moderate. This means that the level of teachers’ perceived organizational support namely: personalized organizational support, collectivistic organizational support, monistic organizational support, and teleological support was moderate and was sometimes observed among teachers of Bangoy District, Davao City Division.

Table 2. Level of Teachers’ Perceived Organizational Support

No.	Item	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Personalized Organizational Support	3.29	Moderate
2	Collectivistic Organizational Support	3.49	High
3	Monistic Organizational Support	3.33	Moderate
4	Teleological Organizational Support	3.39	Moderate
Overall Mean		3.36	Moderate

3.3. *Significant Relationship between School Head’s Motivational Language and Teacher’s Perceived Organizational Support* — Table 3 presented data on the significant correlation between the motivational language used by school heads and teachers’ perceptions of organizational support. To determine the strength of this relationship, the Pearson Product Moment Correlation (Pearson r) was employed. The analysis yielded a p-value of .000, which is below the accepted significance level of .05.

As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a meaningful connection between the variables. These results imply that when school heads utilize more motivational language, teachers tend to perceive higher levels of organizational support. Such communication likely enhances teachers’ feelings of being valued, included, and aligned with the institution’s objectives, thereby enriching their organizational experience. This underscores the vital influence of leadership communication in fostering a supportive educational environment.

Table 3. Significant Relationship Between School Head’s Motivational Language and Teacher’s Perceived Organizational Support

Variables	r-value	Statistical Description	p-value	Decision
Motivational Language (x) Perceived Organizational Support (y)	2*0.83	2*Strong correlation	2*.000*	2*Reject Ho

*Significant at $p < .05$

3.4. *Domains of School Head’s Motivational Language that Significantly Influence Teacher’s Perceived Organizational Support*—Table 4 presents the results of the regression analysis examining the relationship between the school head’s use of motivational language—including direction-giving/uncertainty-reducing language (perlocutionary), empathetic language (illocutionary), and meaning-making language (locutionary)—and teachers’ perceived organizational support. The analysis yielded an overall correlation coefficient (r) of 0.83 with a p-value of less than .000, indicating a strong positive association between the variables, as interpreted using Cohen’s (2002) guidelines. This confirms the hypothesis that a significant relationship exists between the two.

The results clearly suggest a very strong and statistically significant connection between

school heads’ motivational communication and teachers’ perceptions of organizational support. Additionally, an F-value of 68.84 with a p-value below .000 points to the model being a good fit. The R^2 value of 0.6889 indicates that approximately 68.89 percent of the variation in perceived organizational support among teachers can be attributed to the combined influence of the three dimensions of motivational language, with the remaining variance explained by other factors. The regression analysis further reveals that all dimensions of the school head’s motivational language significantly impact teachers’ perceived organizational support. Notably, the unstandardized coefficients show that direction-giving/uncertainty-reducing language exerts the most substantial influence, with a coefficient of $\beta = 0.398$ and a p-value below 0.05, signifying statistical significance. As a result, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table 4. Domains of School Head’s Motivational Language that Significantly Influence Teacher’s Perceived Organizational Support

School Head’s Motivational Language	B	SE	β	t	p	Decision @ $\alpha = .05$
Constant	1.908	0.209	–	4.668	.000	–
Direction-Giving / Uncertainty Reducing	0.398	0.085	0.981	4.565	.000	Reject H_0
Empathetic Language	0.300	0.079	0.601	6.432	.000	Reject H_0
Meaning-Making Language	0.380	0.085	0.102	1.086	.001	Reject H_0

Dependent Variable: Teacher’s Perceived Organizational Support

Model Summary: $R = 0.83$, $R^2 = 0.6889$, $F = 68.844$, $p < .001$

Note. All predictors are statistically significant at the 0.05 level.

4. Discussion

This study aimed to determine the level of school leaders’ motivating language and teachers’ perceived organizational support among public elementary school teachers in the Bangoy District, Davao City Division. In addition, it sought to establish empirical evidence on the relationship

between the motivational language used by school leaders—specifically direction-giving, empathic, and meaning-making language and the organizational support perceived by teachers. Furthermore, the study employed statistical analyses to identify which domains of motivational language significantly influence teachers' perceptions of organizational support. Data were analyzed using Weighted Mean, Pearson r , and Linear Regression to determine levels, relationships, and predictive influences. The following are the significant findings:

4.1. Findings—On the level of school head's motivational language was found to be moderate, which also means that it was sometimes evident. This indicates that while school heads do engage in practices that provide direction, foster empathy, and convey purpose, these efforts are not consistently sustained. This aligns with Burns' Transformational Leadership Theory, suggesting that school leaders are engaging in elements of transformational leadership, but may need to apply motivational language more deliberately and consistently to fully inspire and empower their teaching staff.

On the other hand, the level of teacher's perceived organizational support was described as moderate, which also means that it was sometimes evident. This reveals that teachers feel organizational backing to a fair extent, though not at an optimal level. Through the lens of Social Exchange Theory, this suggests that the reciprocal nature of organizational support is only partially being fulfilled, which may affect teachers' sense of value, trust, and professional commitment. Strengthening the quality and frequency of supportive interactions from school leaders could enhance the perceived balance in this social exchange.

On the results of the test of relationship between the variables involved in the study, the null hypothesis was rejected, confirming a significant relationship between school head's motivational language and teacher's perceived organizational support. This strong positive relationship underscores the importance of lead-

ership communication, supporting Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory by highlighting that motivational factors such as recognition and respect directly contribute to positive perceptions in the workplace. It also reflects how the intentional use of language by school heads can elevate morale and shape a more supportive organizational climate.

Based on the regression analysis, the results revealed that the school head's motivational language significantly influences teacher's perceived organizational support by registering a p -value of .000 which is less than .05 in the level of significance. This finding reinforces the principle of reciprocity in Social Exchange Theory, indicating that when leaders communicate in ways that reduce uncertainty, demonstrate empathy, and help teachers find purpose in their roles, teachers are more likely to feel acknowledged and supported.

Based on the findings, the study recommends fostering open communication between teachers and school heads to enhance support and motivation, using motivational language rooted in Transformational Leadership Theory. The Department of Education is urged to provide training for school leaders to improve communication skills that strengthen organizational commitment and teacher well-being. A positive school culture resulting from these efforts is expected to benefit students through improved engagement and academic success. Future research should explore additional factors influencing organizational support, including cultural and leadership dynamics.

5. References

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